

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ДИФЕРЕНЦИАЛНО – ДИАГНОСТИЧЕН ПОДХОД НА КИШЛИЦАТА ПРИ ДЕЦА

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DIFFERENTIAL – DIAGNOSTIC APPROACH TO COUGH IN CHILDREN

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Резюме

Кашлицата е съпътстващ симптом на широк спектър от болестни състояния в детска възраст (ДВ) и е едно от най – честите оплаквания, за които родителите водят децата си при лекар. И представлява защитен рефлекс, който помага за изчистване на дихателните пътища (ДП) от различни инхалирани химични, механични и биологични дразнители, които активират рецепторите на кашлицата, разположени в мукозата на ДП от ларинкс до респираторните бронхиоли, също така има и екстрапулмонални рецептори, намиращи се в параназалните синуси, външния слухов канал и тимпаничната мембрана, хранопровода, диафрагмата, париталната плевра и перикарда, които реагират основно на механични стимули. Тези рецептори са нервни окончания на вагусовите аферентни нерви, които изпращат сигнали обратно към центъра на кашлицата в продълговатия мозък, който задейства последователност от събития, които предизвикват кашлица. Подходите за контрол на кашлицата трябва да се фокусират върху характеризирането на кашлицата чрез клинична оценка за да се идентифицира точно нейната етиология. Подробната анамнеза и физикалният преглед са крайногелните камъни на оценката на дете с кашлица. При диференциалната диагноза на острата кашлица е съществено да не се пропуснат потенциално животозастрашаващи състояния като белодробен тромбемболизъм и остра сърдечна недостатъчност. Тази статия има за цел да представи подробен диференциално – диатностичен подход на кашлицата в ДВ.

Abstract

Cough is a concomitant symptom of a wide range of childhood (CH) diseases and is one of the most common complaints for which parents take their children to a doctor. It is a protective reflex that helps to clear the airways (AW) from various inhaled chemical, mechanical and biological irritants that activate cough receptors located in the mucosa of the AW from the larynx to the respiratory bronchioles, there are also extrapulmonary receptors located in the paranasal sinuses, external auditory canal and tympanic membrane, esophagus, diaphragm, parietal pleura, and pericardium that respond primarily to mechanical stimuli. These receptors are nerve endings of the vagus afferent nerves that send signals back to the cough center in the medulla oblongata, which triggers a sequence of events that cause cough. Approaches to cough control should focus on characterizing the cough through clinical evaluation to accurately identify its etiology. A detailed history and physical examination are the cornerstones of the evaluation of a child with cough. In the differential diagnosis of acute cough, it is essential not to miss potentially life-threatening conditions such as pulmonary thromboembolism and acute heart failure. This article aims to present a detailed differential-diagnostic approach to cough in the CH.

Ключови думи: Етиология, диагностика, деца, диференциална диагноза, кашлица.

Keywords: Etiology, diagnosis, children, differential diagnosis, cough.

Introduction

Cough is the most common symptom seen in outpatient clinics in many countries, and persistent cough (> 2 weeks) is one of the most common reasons for referral of children to a pediatrician or pediatric pulmonologist. Researchers have found that 35 – 40% of school - aged children continue to cough 10 days after the onset of the common cold, which is a common viral infection of the upper respiratory tract, and 10% of pre-school children continue to cough up to 25 days after a respiratory tract infection. A healthy child may normally cough up to 11 times a day, including in winter when returning home from playing outside in the cold. Cough may also be due to compression of the trachea or n. vagus by enlarged lymph nodes or by mediastinal tumors. The most common cause of acute cough in

childhood is a viral upper respiratory tract (URT) infection, while the most common causes of chronic cough are bronchial asthma, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), and postnasal drip (often secondary to allergic rhinosinusitis). The definition of chronic cough varies across guidelines. It is defined as a persistent and continuous cough lasting more than 4 weeks in the 2020 CHEST consensus, and the British Thoracic Society guideline defines chronic cough in children as one that lasts more than 8 weeks, while also recognizing sub-acute cough that lasts 4–8 weeks.[2][4][5][6][7][8][11][12][13]

Cough classification

Cough is usually classified based on its duration, quality, or etiology. These indicators are important for the differential diagnosis (DD) of cough, (Tables 1, 2).

Cough is classified by its sound pattern as either dry (unproductive) or wet (productive) in nature. Parents are usually able to describe the cough sound pattern or provide recordings of their child's cough. The physician can determine the cough sound pattern when the child coughs spontaneously during examination or by asking her/ him to cough, therefore determining the sound pattern can help to indicate the etiology of the cough. A wet cough suggests mucous hypersecretion or impaired mucociliary clearance as the underlying cause, whereas a dry cough suggests airway irritation or inflammation or a non-airway etiology. In addition, clinicians should be aware that dry cough can become wet when AW secretions increase.[10]Cough is classified by duration as acute (up to 2 weeks), subacute/persistent (up to 4 weeks), or chronic (>4 weeks). Cough is classified by etiology as specific (SC) and nonspecific coughs(NSC). NSC is a dry cough in an unidentified respiratory disease with a known etiology. Most cases of NSC are due to non-serious causes - e.g. post-viral cough, and/or increased sensitivity of cough receptors, which may resolve spontaneously. Whereas SC is associated with other symptoms and signs suggesting an underlying problem.[3][4][5][6] Indicators of the presence of SC are[18]:

- Sudden cough with an episode of shortness of breath
- Progressive cough
- Difficulty breathing chronically or during physical exertion
- Delay in physical development
- Hypoxemia
- Constitutional symptoms
- “Club fingers” and “watch glass” nails
- Hemoptysis
- Chest wall abnormalities

- Noisy breathing and/or unusual auscultatory pulmonary rales
- Cough with a history of recurrent pneumonia
- Cough with onset in the neonatal period
- Difficulty swallowing
- Craniofacial anomaly
- Neuromuscular disease
- Wet cough, lasting more than 3 - 4 weeks.

DD of common causes of cough in children according to its duration.

1. Acute cough (<2 weeks):
 - Classic recognizable cough: Barking cough in laryngotracheobronchitis; Staccato cough in chlamydial infection; Paroxysmal in case of pertussis (whooping cough) and parapertussis; psychogenic cough (dry/barking, absent at night, without clear etiology)
 - Infection of upper/lower respiratory tract
 - Foreign body aspiration (FBA)
 - Bronchial asthma (BA)
 - Inhalation injury in case of acute exposure to smoke or volatile substances.
 - Embolic hemorrhage (rare)
2. Subacute (2-4 weeks) - examples are: postviral cough and acute bronchitis.
3. Chronic (> 4 weeks):
 - Nonspecific cough: Postviral; Increased receptor sensitivity; Bronchial asthma; GERD; Chronic process in the upper respiratory tract;
 - Subacute bronchitis
 - Bronchiectasis and persistent pneumonia: cystic fibrosis; ciliary dyskinesia; immunodeficiency; congenital lung lesions
 - Aspiration
 - Chronic infections: tuberculosis; nontuberculous mycobacteria; mycoses
 - Interstitial lung disease (e.g. rheumatic disease)
 - Cardiac etiology.

Table 1.

Common causes of chronic cough by age (according to Haya Alsubaie at al, 2015)

Young children (<5 years)	Older children (>5 years)
Infections	Bronchial asthma
Postviral hyperreactivity of the Airway	Infections – such as tuberculosis, mycoses, nontuberculous mycobacteria
GERD	Postnasal drip
Congenital malformations of the AW	Recurrent pneumonia
Bronchial asthma	Protracted bacterial bronchitis
Protracted bacterial bronchitis	Passive smoking
Passive smoking	Bronchiectasis
Foreign body aspiration	Psychogenic cough

Table 2.

Classification of classically recognizable cough based on its sound qualities (according to Chang at al, 2006)

Cough characteristic	Possible etiology
Paroxysmal (with or without "whoop") with urge to vomit	Pertussis/pertussis-like syndrome
Dry/barking, laryngeal cough	Acute croup, tracheomalacia, habitual/psychogenic
Staccato cough in infants and young children	Chlamydial infection
Wet/ productive	Protracted bacterial bronchitis, pneumonia, primary ciliary dyskinesia
Morning chronic wet cough	Purulent lung diseases

Differential diagnostic algorithm for cough in childhood.

History and physical examination. A precise history and a thorough physical examination are essential

for the correct preparation of a differential diagnostic plan and subsequent establishment of an accurate etiological diagnosis.

The history should focus on identifying:

- Duration, quality, provoking factors, progression and daily/seasonal variations of the cough, accompanying symptoms, neonatal and family history, history of exposure to harmful environmental factors (passive smoking and air pollutants), medication intake and family and personal history of allergic diseases (BA, allergic rhinitis, allergic rhinosinusitis, atopic dermatitis, etc.). Parents and relatives of children from 6 months to 6 years of age should be asked about the possibility of aspiration of foreign bodies (small toys, small objects, consumption of peanuts, grapes, etc.), the entry of a foreign body into the respiratory tract is often accompanied by the so-called "respiratory choking": during feeding (usually when crying, laughing, playing) a painful attack of coughing suddenly occurs, sometimes with cyanosis and short-term apnea.

- The medical history should include recent respiratory infections, recurrent pneumonia, and questions about risk factors for tuberculosis (TB) - contact with a person who is proven or suspected to have tuberculosis, risk groups for TB are those at higher risk of exposure (have traveled to or immigrated from countries with endemic TB, live in poor conditions or do not have access to health services, such as homeless people, drug addicts, alcoholics).

- Psychogenic cough is characterized by its absence at night and during play and is not accompanied by fever and other symptoms. Paroxysmal cough in case of pertussis (whooping cough) is characterized by a prolonged series of coughing fits, followed by deep and noisy inhalation (whoop) with the release of sticky mucus, sometimes with vomiting.

- Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) in infants and young children is characterized by a history of spitting up after eating, irritability during eating, paroxysmal dystonic postures including torticollis and opisthotonus (Sandifer syndrome), growth retardation, recurrent wheezing or pneumonia, and in older children GERD is characterized by chest pain or heartburn after eating and lying down, night cough, hoarseness, halitosis, abdominal pain and regurgitation.

The physical examination should be directed at the general condition of the child and should include determination of:

- Vital signs and growth parameters, detailed examination of the respiratory system, including ENT status

- Inspection of the chest wall for signs of hyperinflation and deformities

- Inspection for edema, cyanosis, the presence of "Club fingers" and "watch glass" nails, and for recurrent/persistent auscultatory physical findings, indicating chronic lung infections, that occur in children with bronchiectasis, cystic fibrosis, pulmonary congenital anomaly, or lung abscess

- Persistent exudative physical findings on pulmonary auscultation in the same location for months and years are indicative of irreversible morphological changes and are pathognomonic for the presence of

bronchiectasis. Auscultatory findings of crepitations, rhonchi and crackles, indicating pneumonia, bronchiolitis or bronchial obstruction, and bilateral "wheezing" breathing indicates asthma, but may be associated with vascular ring, cystic fibrosis, etc. Persistent unilateral "wheezing" breathing is highly suspicious for FBA. The presence of inspiratory stridor and low or lack of respiratory sounds with or without cyanosis, indicate Croup syndrome.

- Hemoptysis can be observed in bronchiectasis, pulmonary hemosiderosis, hemorrhagic pneumonia in newborns, severe congestion in the small circle of blood circulation in case of left ventricular failure, mitral or aortic valve disease, parasitosis, mycoses, pneumonia, cystic fibrosis, tuberculosis and endobronchial processes.

Investigations.

Investigations that aid in the diagnosis of cough include:

- CBC, differential CBC, ESR, and CRP

- Collection of a sample of the sputum for rapid antigen testing or culture

- Chest radiography may provide information about pulmonary infiltrates/consolidations, pneumothorax, hyperinflation, atelectasis, and chronic pulmonary changes. Lateral or anteroposterior neck radiography is necessary in some unclear cases of croup

- Functional respiratory testing (spirometry) in cooperative children over 6 years of age. This test aids in the diagnosis of restrictive and obstructive lung disease (including it aids in the diagnosis of asthma)

- Mantoux tuberculin skin test as a screening test for tuberculosis infection

- GERD can be proven by pH-metry, sometimes fibroesophagogastroscopy is performed to diagnose anatomical causes of obstruction in the upper parts of the gastroesophageal tract. But in most cases the diagnosis is clinical, and a diagnostic and therapeutic attempt is made with positional treatment and the use of H₂ - inhibitors or proton pump inhibitors.

- Bronchoscopy (or fibrobronchoscopy) allows for assessment of the anatomical structure of the tracheobronchial tree (detection of congenital anomalies, tumors, granulations, foreign bodies); assessment of the condition of the bronchial mucosa (hyperemia, bleeding, erosions); assessment of bronchial secretions - purulent, serous, hemorrhagic, these symptoms are suspicious for bronchiectasis; detection and removal of foreign bodies in the respiratory tract; performing diagnostic and therapeutic bronchoalveolar lavage [2]

- Sweat chloride test in case of clinical and radiological data of cystic fibrosis

- Computed tomography (CT) in case of suspected data of bronchiectasis, tumors, vascular „ring“ anomaly and congenital lung malformations (lung sequestration, etc.)

- In case of chronic wet cough, an attempt can be made to expectorate and examine sputum for cytological, cultural examination and microbial sensitivity, includingly for acid-fast bacilli (AFB)

- Allergy tests: skin allergy tests or specific RAST tests

- Attempt of treatment with antiasthmatic drugs in case of chronic wet cough in young children for a period of 6-8 weeks, after which the same treatment can be discontinued[9].

Recommendations for cases of cough in a child, for which a mandatory consultation with a pediatric pulmonologist is required:

- Chronic wet cough, not responding to antimicrobial therapy
- Cough of unclear etiology and duration of more than 4 weeks
- Chronic cough, accompanied by a lag in physical development and/or associated with persistent hypoxemia
 - Cough with a history of recurrent pneumonia
 - Cough with persistent pulmonary wheezing
 - Cough, accompanied by hemoptysis pointing to an underlying disease, for example, bronchiectasis, pulmonary hemosiderosis, hemorrhagic pneumonia, cystic fibrosis, tuberculosis and endobronchial processes
- Chronic cough associated with bronchial asthma, not responding to maintenance anti-asthmatic therapy.

In conclusion, cases of cough of unclear etiology and duration of more than 4 weeks should be referred for consultation with a pediatric pulmonologist and children with cough should be treated according to disease-specific guidelines. In the differential diagnosis of acute cough, it is essential not to miss potentially life-threatening conditions such as pulmonary thromboembolism, acute heart failure and foreign body aspiration. The treatment of cough in kids to be based on its etiology.

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